

GLOBAL
BIODATA
COALITION

SUSTAINABILITY LAB: WORKSHOP REPORT

Building innovative solutions for
global biodata sustainability

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Executive Summary

The Global Biodata Coalition's (GBC) Sustainability Lab workshop brought together a diverse group of around 30 innovators from a range of disciplines and sectors—with experts in economics, science-of-science, physical sciences, ecological and environmental sciences and data innovation joining biodata resource leaders to bring new thinking and ideas on how to enhance the sustainability of the biodata resource infrastructure.

The workshop formed a key part of GBC's work to take forward its White Paper on Sustainability, which was published in January 2025. The goal of the workshop was to generate and explore a range of ideas that could be considered further by GBC, its member funders, and the biodata resource leaders with which it works. It was intended to act as a call to action around the critical challenge of funding and sustaining the biodata infrastructure, identifying and beginning to build support around potential pilots that could be developed to take forward new ideas.

The Workshop was held over a day and a half in Montreal, Canada on 19-20 August 2025 and was moderated by Research Consulting Ltd. It was a hybrid event, with a majority of participants joining in person and several joining the discussions online. The workshop program is appended at Appendix A and the list of participants at Appendix B.

Expanding the idea pool: identifying potential models

Through a series of case studies, pitch talks and panel discussions, workshop participants presented and discussed a range of potential models and ideas which could potentially be deployed to help build more secure and sustainable funding for biodata resources. Among the ideas discussed were:

- Pooled funding models where public, charitable and private funders contribute to resources in line with usage.
- New economic models that aim to assign value to data and its curation, including the potential application of a cap and trade approach where data and associated services have a value that is traded in credits.
- A range of potential approaches through which revenue could be generated from commercial or other users willing to pay—including providing enhanced access, providing value add services, or providing enterprise-standard versions of products and services ('freemium' models).
- Voluntary membership models of different types and scales where communities contribute to the funding and sustainability of a biodata resource.

- Distributed service models where the costs of curating and preserving data are dispersed across multiple sites under a unified front-end, open source software and metadata standards.
- Public-private partnership models where commercial users work in partnership with biodata resources to develop and maintain data of shared value in the pre-competitive space.

Cross-cutting themes

In discussing these ideas, participants raised a number of critical considerations and cross-cutting themes in developing and testing sustainable funding approaches. These included:

- **Understanding and engaging user communities**—it is critical that biodata resources have approaches in place to know who is using the data, how they are using it and for what purposes—including current and potential future requirements. This should be accompanied by active ongoing engagement with users on their current requirements and emerging needs. This is vital both to identify what approaches to fund and sustain any given resource are most likely to be viable and acceptable for users, and to develop data products that meet user needs and maximise efficiencies—ensuring funding and resources are targeted effectively.
- **Ensuring AI-readiness**—the emergence and proliferation of AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) is a game changer, which brings significant opportunities as well as considerable challenges for biodata resources. Biodata resources need to consider how best to navigate relationships with those building and using these tools and how best to utilise AI approaches in enhancing the services they provide.
- **Rebalancing incentives**—in order to build a more sustainable ecosystem, it is vital to realign incentive and rewards structures to ensure all those who play a key role in generating, managing and enabling the re-use of data are recognised appropriately.
- **Ensuring equity**—equity and fairness must be at the heart of sustainable funding. This incorporates equity in terms of how funding for the biodata infrastructure is provisioned so that those benefiting from the use of biodata resources contribute in a proportionate and fair manner. It also means that the needs of all types of data resources and users (depositors and consumers) in all parts of the world should be taken into account, and that funding allocations do not further contribute to, or exacerbate data accessibility inequities. It is important that these discussions align with ongoing international policy developments, including those relating to access and benefit sharing in the context of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).

- **Demonstrating impact**—biodata resources need to continue to enhance their ability to track and demonstrate their usage and impact and communicate this effectively to funders, policy makers and other stakeholders.
- **Recognising the value of open science**—participants emphasised the value of open science, underpinned by free and unrestricted access to data, in delivering societal benefits. The need for caution in introducing approaches which might compromise this principle, or disadvantage or disenfranchise key groups of existing or future users, was highlighted. It was recognised that there can be ways of generating revenue that build on open models and that there are contexts in which a commercial or managed access approach is viable and appropriate, but careful tensioning is required.
- **Advocating expanded and coordinated funding**—there was a strong feeling from several participants that public funders should take responsibility for supporting biodata resources given their fundamental importance to life science research. There was a view that in parallel with exploring new models for sustainable funding, there needed to be a short term effort to advocate the critical importance of funding data infrastructure to existing funders, and to build mechanisms to better enable cooperative and pooled funding approaches.

Piloting new approaches

Through group discussions, participants workshopped ideas and developed four proposals for pilot projects targeted at key ideas and themes raised during the workshop. It is envisaged that these pilots would run over a 18 month timeframe, and could be taken forward in partnership with funders and biodata resources, including the Global Core Biodata Resources.

1. **Enhancing the AI readiness of biodata:** framework policy & partnerships—Pilot partnerships between an AI company and a specific biodata resource, in which the company provides funding or in-kind support and works in partnership with the resource to enhance the AI-readiness of its data.
2. **Segmented user pays**—Test approaches that keep data/services of broad value openly accessible, whilst establishing specific data subsets or service functions for commercial users or others willing to pay. All approaches should consider equity at the core.
3. **Pooled funding for FAIR AI optimisation**—Develop a service to simplify access to data from a pool of participating biodata resources for commercial users developing LLMs. The commercial user would be asked to contribute pooled funding to support the continued provision of this data stream.

4. Public good in biodiversity monitoring—building high quality and trustworthy global standards across existing biodata resources for collection of biodiversity data in a way that enhances the value of these data for global biodiversity monitoring and hence enhances the value and sustainability of these resources.

Conclusions and Next Steps

Biodata resource sustainability is a complex challenge to which there is no single solution. As highlighted in the GBC's White Paper, given the huge variation amongst biodata resources and amongst funders a range of different approaches and models will be required. The workshop provided a clear demonstration of the contribution that experts outside the biosciences can bring to these discussions, generating a wealth of valuable ideas and examples for further exploration and discussion.

As noted above, there was a clear view that whilst there is a pressing need to explore new ideas and models, particularly as advances in AI continue to transform the landscape, these will take time to bear fruit. Many biodata resources of global importance to life science research face urgent and existential funding challenges, and there is a need for funders around the world to contribute sustained and cooperative funding for biodata infrastructure.

The GBC will take forward discussions with funders, biodata resources and its wider stakeholder community to build on the outcomes of this workshop, seeking to work in partnership to further develop, pilot and test the ideas and models proposed. It will also continue to advocate the critical importance of biodata infrastructure and work to expand the breadth of funders engaged in its work.

Sustainability Lab: Building Innovative Solutions for Global Biodata Sustainability

The Global Biodata Coalition's (GBC) Sustainability Lab workshop took place in Montreal Canada on 19-20 August 2025, and brought together a diverse group of innovators from a range of disciplines and sectors to share and develop a range of ideas, exemplars and models that could be considered to enhance the sustainability of the global biodata resource infrastructure.

Workshop participants shared and explored ideas through a series of short talks, plenary and small group discussions. After an introductory session, participants presented their perspectives and ideas via a series of case study presentations, pitches and lightning talks. In the second part of the meeting, participants broke into small groups to explore key themes and ideas and articulate potential pilot projects. The meeting closed with a final plenary discussion to draw together the ideas discussed and consider next steps.

Setting the scene

Participants were welcomed to the meeting by Guy Cochrane, GBC Executive Director, and Phil Bourne, University of Virginia and Chair of the GBC Scientific Advisory Committee—who outlined the genesis and objectives of the workshop.

The Global Biodata Coalition was established in 2019 by a consortium of research funders. It provides a forum for funders to better coordinate and share approaches for the efficient management and growth of biodata resources worldwide, and aims to stabilise and ensure sustainable financial support for the global biodata infrastructure. As a key element of its work, the GBC works with a set of 52 Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBRs), identified through two selection rounds held in 2022 and 2023, GCBRs are resources that demonstrate global usage and impact, and whose long-term sustainability is of critical importance to the global research endeavour in the life sciences and biomedicine.

In January 2025, GBC published a White Paper setting out a framework for developing cooperative approaches to fund and sustain biodata resources. It identifies nine key principles to help guide the development of such approaches and a series of potential models that build on these principles.

The proposals were based on the findings of a cross-funder working group and extensive consultation with resource leaders and the wider research data community. The White Paper recognised the need to consider longer-term, more transformative approaches, alongside approaches which could have a more immediate impact in addressing the funding and sustainability of biodata resources.

Work developed by Johnson and Bourne has explored one such model. They argue that with the rapid rates of data production and accumulation, current economic models for funding biodata resources will not scale. With the rate of research funding essentially flat, there is an inherent paradox, in that rising costs of managing data will mean that supporting it will divert money from supporting new research, whilst at the same time these data hold tremendous potential to enable innovation. They propose an alternative model (coined 'Sustainability 2.0') that is based on a 'cap and trade' approach which places a cap on the amount of funding, and assigns a monetary value to data, which is traded in credits. This work demonstrated the value of engaging experts from outside the biosciences to bring new perspectives and ways of thinking to the biodata sustainability challenge.

The Sustainability Lab workshop aimed to further stimulate and develop such a dialogue, bringing together biodata resource leaders with a diverse group of innovators from outside the life sciences. This was not a decision meeting: the goal was not to recommend a single preferred mechanism to take forward, but rather to explore a range of ideas which GBC and other stakeholders could consider alongside the models proposed in the White Paper. The workshop was also intended as a call to action to focus attention on the critical importance of biodata resource sustainability and generate momentum in testing and implementing cooperative approaches. A specific goal was to identify pilots or other actions that could be taken forward to further test and implement new and innovative approaches.

Defining the Challenge

Guy Cochrane and Dario Taraborelli of the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative provided brief perspectives to introduce the nature of the funding and sustainability challenge.

Researchers in the life sciences and biomedicine are critically dependent on a global infrastructure of biodata resources, which store, curate and provide access to the data generated by research and tools to enable these data to be combined and reused. The resources that make up this infrastructure are highly connected but dispersed and the infrastructure has grown organically over time with no top-down coordination.

Many biodata resources are supported primarily by public and charitable funding bodies through short-term competitive grants. This reliance on short-term funding inhibits the ability of resources to plan strategically and to attract and retain skilled staff. To illustrate this point, data collected by the GBC for 42 of the 52 GCBRs indicates that only 50 per cent of staff positions deployed in maintaining these resources have funding sources that are assured beyond four years.

The funding mechanisms that are available to biodata resources are often not well geared to their needs. Biodata resources typically don't produce the types of outputs funders expect from research, and funding mechanisms often focus on supporting innovation rather than ongoing operation and service delivery. Indeed, for many funders, building new infrastructure may be more attractive than taking on the operational and technical debt associated with an existing resource. Funders currently lack the tools to manage what is a fragmented landscape and often find it challenging to fund cooperatively, with many public funders not able to fund outside a defined national or regional jurisdiction.

In addition, biodata resources are facing increasing challenges, perhaps most notably the rapid growth of AI and Large Language Models (LLMs), which offer opportunities and challenges for resources in terms of ensuring data is AI-ready. This also highlights the perception of a "free-riding" issue, where commercial entities use freely available open data in the context of AI and other commercial applications for great profit, but do not seem to contribute proportionately towards the cost.

The value of funders working with biodata resources to help them undertake user analyses was emphasised. This can help resources to identify their competitive strengths and drive change. It was suggested that the current funding available from public and charitable sources should be seen as fixed, and there was a need to look for synergies across sectors and develop new mechanisms for cross-sector funding. New types of partnerships and funding mechanisms that bring together public and private sector support in the pre-competitive space will be required.

Case studies: Implementing innovative solutions to develop and sustain data services

Four case studies were presented to highlight the experiences of four data services which had implemented innovative approaches to enhance their funding and sustainability. Presenters focused on the benefits, challenges and lessons learned.

- **Radiant Earth** is a non-profit dedicated to creating a shared understanding of the world through initiatives that make data easier to access and use. One key example has been Landsat 8 satellite data which produces images in the form of “scenes” each comprising around 1GB of data across 8 TIFF files. It was recognised that most users were downloading huge volumes of image data, but only actually using a fraction of this data. Through enabling users to request individual files and through the use of internal tiling to produce cloud-optimized Geo-TIFF images, it was possible to provide users with rapid and targeted access to the data they required. This demonstrates the need for resources to consider the ergonomics of the data they provide and listen to the data practitioners. Data resources must be agile, they should start with a few products and be prepared to learn quickly and move where needed—maintaining backwards compatibility where possible but being willing to grasp opportunities as they arise.
- **Addgene** is a non-profit biorepository which provides expert curated and quality-assured biomaterials (including plasmids, viral vectors, recombinant antibodies and pooled libraries), a data hub and educational resources. It operates on a cost recovery model: the majority of the biomaterials it distributes are created by scientists (depositors) who retain IP but give Addgene rights to distribute to other scientists in more than 100 countries worldwide. Addgene holds multiple data types—including genetic sequence and associated experimental data for biomaterials which it maintains, providing access to the curated bulk dataset via data licenses. For the sustainability of Addgene’s data, funding is necessary but not sufficient: it requires the integration of data and services, tailored to Addgene user needs. Community-driven value creation is also achieved via a developer portal where Addgene users can access and build applications on the data that maximise its value to science. Addgene’s approach for providing access to data aims to strike a balance between openness, control and discoverability, ensuring the “right data, right users, right access paths” with access controls and licenses for programmatic access to the data and rate-limiting web scraping.

The growth of AI and LLM technologies has created welcome opportunities in terms of enhancing the reach of Addgene's data but has also presented concerns around how data is being used and weakened the control and visibility of biorepositories.

- **Phoenix Bioinformatics** is a non-profit which provides data tools and services for the global research community. It runs the TAIR and MorphoBank knowledgebases. The TAIR database uses an asymmetric subscription model, with a tiered pricing structure where commercial users subsidise access for academic users, a high proportion of which receive complimentary access. MorphoBank uses a voluntary institutional membership model. The membership model is effective but labour-intensive and dependent upon scale and scope, relying on community contributions and keeping costs low. Understanding the user base is critical: not through considering an aggregate average user, but recognising the different motivations that exist across different types of users, and amongst funders and the Phoenix team. Requirements are very different to run a subscription service compared to a grant-funded resource, and TAIR has changed significantly in making this transition. It has several hundred contracts in place, is treated like a vendor and its staffing composition has shifted to incorporate sales and other functions.
- **Open Targets** is a public-private partnership to transform drug discovery through the systematic identification and prioritisation of targets. It is co-funded by EMBL-EBI, the Wellcome Sanger Institute and GSK, with other members currently including Sanofi, Pfizer, MSD and Genentech. The partners work together to define collaborative projects for target identification, which draw on the skills and knowledge of partners, and utilise data from a range of public repositories. The derived data is made public, but partners have pre-publication access as well as access to the Open Targets team, in addition to a voice in setting strategy. Open Targets interacts with more than 40 data resources, and has helped to enhance the interoperability of these resources and close gaps in standardisation. Open Targets has been operating successfully for more than 10 years—attracting new partners to enhance its sustainability, enabling collaborative research and helping champion and provide benefits to the informatics infrastructure. It faces challenges relating to uncertainties of funding and the sometimes rapidly changing priorities of Pharma partners. Its model is size-limiting in that it can become less attractive to companies as more partners join and influence is diluted. This partnership has succeeded as it addresses a key challenge in the pre-competitive space that acted as a catalyst for collaboration, and funding to maintain its data platform was a key part of the collaboration agreement from the outset.

Perspectives of Biodata Resource Leaders

In the next session, a panel of leaders of major biodata resource institutes and initiatives presented their perspectives on the biodata sustainability challenge.

- **EMBL-EBI** hosts and manages a highly connected group of deposition databases and knowledge bases providing open and unrestricted access to users. At present, short term funding models lead to siloes and some funders view support as a one-off rather than a sustained commitment. EMBL-EBI has a mixed funding model, underpinned by core funding from EMBL, with project-based funding via a range of grants to develop resources in line with emerging and future needs. The funding model for the Europe PMC resource is one example where funders have taken shared responsibility, and a coalition of funders provide support in proportion to their research spend. Wellcome has recently moved to providing a block award to EMBL-EBI which it can use flexibly to support resources that are strategically important to the funder. This new model will enable EMBL-EBI to work with Wellcome on agreed strategic goals. It will enable new synergies and efficiencies across resources, and explore emerging issues around multimodal data, including the move from considering linear genomes to pan-genomes.
- **The SIB Swiss Institute for Bioinformatics** hosts a range of open data resources with core funding from the Swiss government (SERI). The resources at SIB run on fundamental open science principles, and whilst the Swiss Government is committed to stimulating commercial innovation and R&D, it supports this via different routes. It was emphasised that there are important distinctions between data and other tangible goods, in particular the low marginal costs of sharing and the challenges of charging for data on a use basis. In addition, many SIB resources are run in collaboration with other public funders who apply similar open science principles. If funders believe these resources are a global public good, then there is an argument that they should provide dedicated funding to support them and the expert curators, developers and other specialist staff required to run them adequately as an integral part of their activities.
- **The Leibniz Institute DSMZ** runs a range of biodata resources, and has developed these over a 15-year period to a state where they are now funded publicly on a permanent basis. Over this time, the Institute was able to make the case to the German Government that these resources were central to science, filled an important gap, had high quality standards and the means to make data AI ready. The Institute generates one third of its revenue from selling cultures, and sends out 43,000 items a year to 10,000 customers in 80 countries. The Institute generates one third of its revenue from selling cultures, and sends out 43,000 items a year to 10,000 customers in 80 countries.

Governments across Europe are committed to the value of securing public databases and making data open. It is important to clearly distinguish the types of work that should be supported by public funding and run on open principles and those that are fundable by more commercialised models, and not to mix these models.

- **ELIXIR** is an intergovernmental organisation of 21 member states, which support a central hub and national data nodes, including work to integrate resources and establish standards. ELIXIR works to designate Core Data Resources, which formed the template for the process that GBC uses to designate Global Core Biodata Resources at global level. ELIXIR works closely with industry partners, but believes infrastructure should primarily be resourced by public and other funders. ELIXIR published a [position paper](#) in June 2025 on the importance of open data infrastructures for European competitiveness in life sciences with input from GBC. Work is underway across European infrastructures to develop a broader White Paper activity, with input from the European Commission. The European Commission has extensive plans to further develop open science infrastructure that draw together research and societal data. There are useful models in the health space, such as that developed by Genomics England—where data is held centrally, used by academia and health services and paid for by both sides.

What Can We Learn from Other Disciplines and Sectors?

Participants with expertise spanning a range of disciplines presented short “pitches” in which they proposed an idea, exemplar or way of approaching the biodata sustainability challenge based on their expertise and experience in their fields.

Building on the unique strengths of the biosciences

Cameron Neylon of Curtin University made three key points in his pitch. The first was to draw a distinction between biosciences and other disciplines. He challenged the perception that major infrastructures such as the Square Kilometer Array or CERN could and should be replicated in the biosciences. These are single instruments with data flows, whereas in biosciences, data comes from and into multiple places and is used for multiple purposes. Biosciences is way ahead and is in this position due to sustained investment by funders in data infrastructures for general community use, something other disciplines have not seen.

Second, there are successful examples of public-private partnerships and membership models but these tend to only work where commercial organisations are genuinely part of a community or where there is a contractual relationship where private interests are held at a distance (CrossRef is one such example). Third, there is a general need for more effective financial, technical and legal frameworks to coordinate and ensure value is captured for data. It feels for many as though the level of innovation has tailed off compared to that from 10-15 years ago. Arguably this is due to a lack of capacity in the underpinning data systems due to constrained resources. Fundamentally, this makes an argument for doubling down and continuing the shift for biosciences away from project based individual work towards more integrated models that have delivered innovation.

Creating an effective market that aligns incentives and recognises value

Terry Johnson of the University of Virginia provided his perspective as an economist on the need to act decisively to secure the future of science for humanity. He highlighted how the current situation regarding biodata could reflect many of the key reasons why markets fail, in particular:

- **Positive Externalities:** Data are immensely valuable, but their creation and curation is not rewarded in the existing scholarly incentive system
- **Missing Markets:** Data are decentralized and scattered across different repositories, with rapidly rising data volumes and challenges for curation and standardization
- **Incomplete Information:** It can be difficult to catalog the contents of data and ensure their quality.
- **Market Power:** There are a variety of powerful stakeholders and institutions in the public and private sectors; unintended consequences from intervention might centralize control over data in undesirable ways

He noted that if the costs of curation fail to scale with science and the market for curated data remains decentralised, data will be lost or unusable. His proposal was for a system based on cap and trade that redirects scientific effort towards stewardship of valuable data resources, aligning social and private incentives for data creation and curation in a way that scales with the scientific enterprise. Rather than charge subscription fees that exclude scientists, this allows them to trade time for access, thereby leaving the raw data available to anyone. At the centre of this approach is a data cycle in which scientists exchange data credits for curated data and receive data credits for making novel contributions. Scientists can also do curation work on data they are experts on to earn credits. Other actors can pay to acquire data credits for research.

Some of these funds would be used to support data infrastructure, and some given to data depositors/curators as a reward for their work. This creates an exchange economy around scarce financial resources in which high quality data is incentivised. It is recognised that this proposal raises several major challenges and concerns around logistical complexity, introduction of money into the system, risks of unintended consequences (such as mining for credits through superficial or insufficient data curation), and concerns over equity and how benefits are distributed. However, it provides a starting point for discussion.

Mapping and realigning incentives

Alex Gates of the University of Virginia brought a science-of-science perspective to issues around scientific incentives. He highlighted the need to develop an ecosystem-wide view of biodata usage and the importance of metadata. At present, as more and more data is generated, more and more value results from making connections between datasets. Several different groups have key roles: data contributors, data curators, data cleaners and data users and at present all attention goes to contributors. We need to think about how to attribute credit to all parties and better understand the value of combining datasets. There are a number of emerging tools and systems to enable this—including the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) and badge systems. He concluded that to sustain the value of data we must invest in visibility, traceability and recognition of the people and processes behind them and address the inequalities in credit attribution systems.

Considering the application of distributed service models

Lars Vilhuber of Cornell University provided his thoughts as an economist and statistician on the potential application of distributed service models, which employ a coordinated front end and distributed back-end systems and utilise open source extensive software. One example is the Borealis system of federated Canadian Dataverses, with local collection managers responsible for curation and preservation, feeding into a coordinated front-end API. A second example is the Quantitative Data Repository (QDR), which uses a highly adapted version of Dataverse. A third example is CLOCKSS and CodeOcean, with the former preserving scholarly content across a range of partners and the latter using CLOCKSS for storage: data is distributed but there is a mechanism to surface it. Distributed access models can provide a cost-effective solution and offer a range of benefits: coordination of front ends can aid marketing and resilience, distributed back ends spread costs across a range of partners, and open source extensible software reduces the cost of customisation. Coordinated metadata is an essential pre-requisite for this model.

Creating a Bloomberg terminal for the biosciences

Ryan Hill of Northwestern University provided a perspective as an economist who studies the scientific process. He noted that information was expensive to create but cheap to share and that public goods create free-riding with consumers of data playing little to no part in maintaining it. In terms of how greater private investment in data could be secured, there are three possible options. The first option is to tax industry to subsidise public data: this is done already but could be strengthened further. The second option is to sell priority access: innovators compete fiercely for priority and even a small head start is extremely valuable in a patent race. As an example, universities pay upwards of \$1 million for institutional membership to the Sloan Sky Digital Survey, which includes priority data access. A third option is to co-invest with industry in premium data services. Here the Bloomberg terminal is a valuable comparator: this provides data which is largely publicly available but serves to aggregate dispersed data, provides exclusive data with licensed partners, gives access to proprietary analytics and offers extra speed, storage, and processing power. The second and third options sacrifice some openness to address the free-rider problem. The advent of AI may create opportunities to create services that leverage private sector collaboration to help ensure sustainability.

Applying a Red Hat model to data services

Rebecca Boyles, Deputy Director of RENCI at the University of North Carolina Chapel Hill proposed a hybrid economic model based on that used by the iRODS consortium. The iRODS Consortium was established by RENCI in 2013 to ensure sustainability, development and expansion of the iRODS middleware. It maintains both a public community release and a rigorously tested and hardened “enterprise” version which is sold with support and stability guarantees and emulates the Red Hat model. All code remains open source.

The key components of the model are:

- Core public or grant-based funding to ensure baseline operations, standards, and equitable access.
- Consortium membership fees from academic institutions, industry, and public entities to provide stability and stakeholder buy-in.
- Value-added service subscriptions, offering enterprise-grade support, training, and consulting.
- Open-source “community code” development, supported by active user contributions to keep innovation vibrant and inclusive.

The model allows for diversified funding with a steady flow of revenue as members join and leave, and enables open source innovation whilst also providing commercial-grade reliability. It attracts both public and industry investment, aligning interests and resources. Potential challenges relate to establishing robust and fair governance structures, clarifying agreements around membership levels and benefits, managing code release cycles and securing initial seed funding or transitional grants.

Moving from Sensors to Tensors

Alex Szalay of Johns Hopkins University provided a perspective as an astronomer. He introduced the Sloan Sky Digital Survey and the Skyscanner database, noting that astronomy had rapidly adapted to open data. He highlighted game-changing astronomy databases and noted the AstroPath project which is applying principles from astronomy to dramatically increase data collection in cancer biology. He argued that it is informative to consider the relative value, price and cost of scientific data. Data is all that remains at the end of an experiment—it must be offered through smart services and someone must take ownership and pay for its preservation. Different agencies have different approaches and there is little coherence: we need to move incrementally towards a distributed system with no single point of failure. In terms of the application of AI, academia cannot compete with industry in terms of agility, but can offer tenacity and high-value data. Innovative uses of AI will optimize experiments (sensors) and discover new patterns but this requires the data sets to be “AI-ready” (tensors).

Open Idea Forum

Following the pitch talks, other invited participants had the opportunity to present short lightning talks to provide an idea, exemplar or brief perspectives on addressing the sustainability challenge. Topics addressed by lightning talks included:

Global Equity and Benefit Sharing

Participants highlighted the importance of ongoing global policy discussions at UN-level on Access and Benefit Sharing, particularly to Digital Sequence Information (DSI) on genetic resources, which flows from the Nagoya Protocol under the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD). These recognise the rights of nations to benefit from the use of genetic information on their sovereign biodiversity. At the 16th Conference of Parties (COP16) to the CBD, details of a new multilateral mechanism were agreed under which open sharing of data would continue, but large commercial users of genetic information from public databases, within defined sectors, would be required to pay a proportion of profits or revenues into a common fund, known as the Cali Fund. Funds raised through this mechanism will be distributed equitably towards support for conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, with a particular focus on the needs of developing countries and of indigenous peoples and local communities. The UN Commission on Genetic Resources in Food and Agriculture, a parallel process to the CBD, recently pointed to the importance of open exchange of genetic sequence information required for identification of microorganisms and invertebrates. There is a time-critical opportunity to input into these discussions, and ensure that sustainability of biodata resources is taken into account.

GBIF as an intergovernmental funding model

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is a data infrastructure funded by governments around the world that provides open access to data about all types of life on Earth. Core funding is provided by participating nations (known as Voting Participants) based on a target budget, with annual contributions distributed in proportion to GDP, including a cap of 15% of budget for any one country and 50% discounts for developing countries. This model has provided a steady income stream which has sustained GBIF for more than 24 years. It is equitable and avoids over-dependencies on any single country. It also has its challenges in that funding is flat or at best very slightly incremental, whilst data volumes and demand continue to grow. Government priorities can shift rapidly, and as with other open resources there are concerns that there are users who are profiting from the use of the resource that are not contributing to its development. GBIF already supplements its core funding with additional sources including project funds from public sector and philanthropic donors. It works continuously to broaden its funding base to support growth and innovation, and to enable capacity development in various global regions.

NEON's experience as a major ecological infrastructure

Funded by the US National Science Foundation, the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON) is a continental-scale observatory designed to enable understanding and forecasting of impacts of environmental change by providing open, long-term, high quality, standardized data, with over 600 staff, 600,000 samples and over 180 data products. In 2024, NEON data were used to train AI models, which have the potential to provide significant revenue to commercial providers. In recognition of this, NEON's Science, Technology & Education Advisory Committee (STEAC) recommended as a first step, to implement user authentication. This will allow NEON to get a better understanding of who is using the data, what data they are using, and for what purposes, in order to consider its approach for sustainability.

The US National Phenology Network exploring alternative funding pathways

The US National Phenology Network (NPN) serves to develop community capacity and practises to monitor plant and animal phenology. The NPN has a programme to develop pathways towards self-sufficiency, as public funding has become more vulnerable and is likely to remain so in the near future. NPN engaged a team of experts to advise on opportunities to generate commercial revenue, but this proved much easier said than done. Infrastructure in institutions to support cost recovery was lacking and there were other actors in the space that are producing products. Whilst a commercial offering that could sustain NPN was not felt to be feasible, private philanthropy was seen as a potential option, but the preference of many funders to build new things rather than sustain existing operations was a challenge.

The potential role of the World Data Service

The World Data Service (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council which serves to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of member data repositories and data services. In its 2025-2027 delivery plan, WDS plans to provide services and support to member repositories, advance the value narratives of its members and advocate for the trustworthiness and FAIRness of member repositories. Members are required to be CoreTrustSeal accredited. The WDS could play a valuable role in helping develop new partnerships with regard to sustainable funding and could be an important group to engage.

The need to demonstrate value and develop better impact narratives

Multiple speakers mentioned the need for biodata resources to develop compelling narratives on the impact of data and to assess the costs, benefits and return on investment. It was noted that these analyses should consider the relationship between data and physical samples. It was also important to identify a full range of values which data hold, with parallels drawn to natural capital accounting. In addition to a monetary value, there is also a sovereignty and national security value for data which should be taken into account.

The role of publishers and data publication

It was important to consider data publications and the Data Processing Charge model being adopted by publishers and curated data services such as Dryad as part of this discussion. When considering the long tail of data, there is a 'sweet spot' in the middle for data associated with projects which has value and is often not currently surfaced and might be amenable to these publication routes. These might also offer incentives for curators and others associated in the generation of these datasets. Publishers can also play a role in surfacing and preserving 'negative' results and other data which are currently lost. For example, Gigascience has partnered with GBIF and WHO on targeted data mobilisation campaigns which have had considerable success.

Prioritising and Workshopping Ideas

During the workshop, the meeting facilitators captured the key ideas and examples presented throughout the talks and discussion and grouped these under a series of eight themes. In order to help focus and prioritise ideas for more in-depth discussion, participants were asked to vote on the ideas and themes they felt were of greatest interest and relevance for further exploration at the workshop.

Participants then split into four breakout groups, each of which considered two of the eight themes, as follows:

- **Group 1** considered frameworks for collective responsibility, policy frameworks and other ideas.
- **Group 2** considered user pays and subscription models and market-based and incentive models.
- **Group 3** considered pooled and coordinated funding models and public-private partnerships.
- **Group 4** considered public good and infrastructure models and distributed service models.

The breakout group discussions proceeded over two sessions. In the first session, each group held a general discussion around the themes and ideas that had arisen during the workshop, focusing on those with the most votes from participants. They considered the benefits of the ideas or theme, the challenges, the key stakeholders that needed to be engaged and how the idea or ideas might be piloted and evaluated.

In the second discussion session, groups focused on a specific idea for a pilot that could potentially be supported by GBC, with engagement from GBC member funders and the Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBRs). The aim was for pilots to provide an insight into, or movement toward, greater sustainability of biodata resources and have defined success criteria and metrics. The approximate scale should be to occupy 1 or 2 FTEs over a timescale of around 18 months. Summaries of the pilots proposed by the four groups follow below.

Pilot 1: Enhancing the AI-readiness of biodata: framework policy & partnerships

This pilot would seek to build partnerships between biodata resources and AI companies. The AI companies would provide some funding and potentially also in-kind contributions of staff and tools to assist the biodata resource in making data fully AI-ready and in working with the company to develop domain-specific LLMs or small language models (SLMs).

As resources are typically not in a position to make these connections, it was proposed that GBC could consider recruiting a development manager to build these relationships. As a first step to building these partnerships, a listening workshop or Request for Proposals could be developed. Ideally, it was proposed that GBC should seek to support 3–4 biodata resources to develop and trial such partnerships in a variety of domains, with different types of AI providers. The pilot would need to be underpinned by a policy framework defining the conditions for data exchange and benefits.

The pilot would bring benefits to resources in terms of funding and resources, and a broader understanding and template for how partnerships and revenue streams with AI providers could be developed. The benefit to the company is that the quality and readiness of the data would be enhanced. The potential risks relate to uncertainties as to whether AI companies will be prepared to engage and whether the relationships can be sustained over time. Whilst there is a potential risk that the additional funding may displace existing public funding, there is arguably a greater risk of relying on continued funding under the status quo.

Pilot 2: Segmented user pays

This pilot would aim to support biodata resources to test approaches that keep data of broad interest openly accessible, whilst establishing specific data subsets or services for commercial use. Equity considerations should be at the heart of any approaches that are tested: it should involve direct engagement with equity-deserving groups and potentially adopt a governance structure with representation from these communities. The first step in any pilot would be for participating biodata resources to gain a full understanding of who their users are and how they are using the data. This would likely involve setting up a system that allows for segmentation of users into different groups—requiring them to say who they are and what they would use the data for. This will help in the identification of use cases and value propositions.

In terms of the specific approaches that are implemented, there is a spectrum of potential options, and it is likely that different approaches will be amenable to different resources. This could include voluntary payments (donations), licence models where certain users pay a one-off fee or managed access approaches with limits on bulk downloads and APIs.

Pilot 3: Pooled funding for FAIR AI optimisation

This pilot would aim to develop an aggregated service to simplify access to AI-ready data from a group of participating biodata resources for commercial users developing LLMs, and then test these users' willingness to contribute towards a pooled funding mechanism. The pilot would seek to bring together a group of GCBRs or other biodata resources who could pool data into an AI-ready data stream. This would help to generate trust amongst the resources and user communities. Once established, funding contributions would be sought from companies using the data service, which would be distributed across the pool of participating resources to enhance sustainability.

This pilot would seek to build communities and generate a better understanding of the requirements of AI users. It was felt that contributing users are most likely to be industry players: it could be extended to public funders, but this might not be possible within an 18 month time horizon. The key risks are that industry players are not willing to engage or not willing to contribute pooled funding contributions once the interface is enhanced.

The pilot could be evaluated by comparing aggregate user data. It was not felt to be necessary to introduce user registration. A technical specification to achieve aggregation without adding a significant technical burden on participating resources would be a key initial deliverable. It was noted that there are existing projects exploring similar mechanisms and that there might be good opportunities to build upon and partner with these efforts.

Pilot 4: Public good in biodiversity monitoring

The final pilot proposal was to explore the scope and impact of developing a small adaptation on top of existing data resources to achieve high quality and trustable global standards and workflows for the collection and use of biodiversity data. This would seek to address an emerging global need, identified through the CBD process and other international discussions, to develop a global monitoring system for biodiversity, akin to the global meteorological system, and in particular the role that eDNA or metabarcoding will play in such a system. It would seek to define standards for reference data across a group of participating resources and bring this together.

The pilot would bring together relevant biodata resources—including GCBRs and others—to define the standards, develop a proof of concept and assess the cost-benefit. This would likely involve developing protocols for improving data quality and data integration across specimen and observation data (like that in GBIF), DNA sequence data (like that in BOLD and GenBank) and tools for eDNA and metabarcoding.

This would make the results of eDNA and metabarcoding for environmental monitoring more reliable and higher quality than those resulting from the current, fragmented approach. If successful, this could enhance the value of the biodata resources holding this data and support wider re-use of the data, including for citizen science. As such it would contribute to advancing the sustainability of the participating data resources through increasing their impact. It would serve the global public good by building out the data and methodological standards so users can build new tools.

Reviewing the pilot proposals

Participants discussed the set of pilot proposals that emerged. There was some concern that some of the ideas were focusing unduly on adding new features to resources (particularly Pilot 4), and questions over whether the priority should be to secure existing resources and functions, rather than to pursue these types of projects.

Much of the discussion then focused on segmented user pays approaches (Pilot 2). There was a view that there were compelling reasons why user registration had not been adopted by many resources, and that there was likely to be significant resistance to this. It was noted that resources have processes to understand their user bases that don't rely on registration. There was an opposing view that this resistance may be coming largely from within, and the assumption of resistance from users might not play out in practice. Without fully understanding and engaging user communities, resources may be missing significant opportunities to generate revenue and enhance their sustainability. Registration could serve solely to segment users and the purpose they were accessing the data rather than seek to identify them.

There was a strong view from several participants that going down the path of registration and user pays models ran counter to the principles of open science and a feeling it could create barriers to the integration and re-use of data that impact basic research. Whilst fully acknowledging these concerns and that this approach will not be suitable for all resources, others felt pilots would be useful to test these assumptions and how users react in reality. Several participants cited examples where user registration requirements have been introduced and initial concerns did not play out in practice. Nonetheless, it was noted that existing resources may be unwilling to take the risk of testing measures which may damage the trust of their existing user bases.

It was suggested that the way that users access resources and data is likely to change fundamentally over the coming five to ten years (with increasing access to combined data streams via LLMs rather than via individual resources), so concerns over any strain the potential pilots place on existing resources may be missing the point.

There was a counter view that the data provided by resources to capture and annotate data will be needed more than ever in five years. Whilst there was a feeling that it was important not just to ensure the existing infrastructure survives but to build a better ecosystem for the future, there is no magic bullet. Whilst there may be some parts of the infrastructure where private funding could play a role, continued public funding would be essential. It was also felt that AI development should not be left exclusively to the private sector and much could be done in the public domain.

Next steps

The closing session of the meeting began with a brief update on a new initiative being taken forward by the US National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine (NASEM) titled Resilient and Enduring Data Infrastructure for Biomedical and Life Sciences Research and Innovation (REDI). REDI will aim to promote collective action and develop a framework to guide sustainable, purpose-driven data infrastructure for biomedical and life science research and innovation. It will consist of two workstreams. The first will seek to develop best practices for managing data across its lifecycle and develop a framework for decision making to inform strategic prioritisation of data resources. The second strand will support experimentation towards the future database ecosystem. The GBC and NASEM will continue to work together as they develop their activities, and the REDI initiative will provide one route for further exploration of the ideas discussed at the workshop.

In closing the workshop, Guy Cochrane and Phil Bourne noted that in addition to the development of a report summarising the workshop, the GBC would explore the potential to develop a paper in which workshop participants could be co-authors. As a further immediate action, GBC would take the summary of the workshop discussions, including the potential pilots, to a joint meeting of the GBC Board, Scientific Advisory Committee and GCBR Forum to be held in early October 2025.

It was clear that whilst a huge range of interesting ideas and models had been discussed, participants had not aligned around a single innovative idea or set of ideas, and the initial pilots that had been proposed were arguably exploring modest adaptations rather than transformative solutions. It was felt that this was to be expected given the complex nature of the sustainability challenge. There will not be a single solution: a range of different approaches will be needed given the huge diversity between different types of data resources and different types of funders.

Testing, refining and building community support around new models will take time. As such, there will be a need to combine efforts to work with funders to maintain and expand funding for biodata resources with longer-term initiatives to develop and pilot new types of approaches.

In closing, Guy and Phil thanked the organising committee, meeting moderators and GBC Secretariat team and all of the participants for their thoughtful contributions and passion over the two days of discussion.

Appendix A: Workshop Program

Day One (Tuesday, 19 August 2025)

08:45-09:15	Welcome & Introductions How did we get here and what do we want to achieve?
09:15-09:45	The Biodata Sustainability Challenge: defining the problem What is the nature of the problem, who are the key stakeholders and why do we need new ideas?
09:45-10:30	Case studies: Implementing innovative solutions to develop and sustain data services Four cases studies to provide exemplars of how innovative approaches to support data services have been identified, piloted and implemented
10:30-11:00	Break
11:00-11:30	View from Biodata Resource Leaders What approaches are major biodata resource leaders implementing or considering to enhance sustainability?
11:30-12:30	What Can We Learn from Other Disciplines and Sectors ? (part 1) Participants will provide short 'pitches' to present an idea, model or approach based on experience from a discipline or sector that could be applied to enhance biodata sustainability:
12:30-13:30	Lunch

13:30-14:00	<p>What Can We Learn from Other Disciplines and Sectors? (part 2)</p> <p>Participants reflect on and discuss the pitches as a whole, and the component ideas that might hold the greatest promise.</p>
14:00-15:00	<p>Open Idea Forum: Lightning Talks</p> <p>Participants will have the opportunity to present a 2-3 minute lightning talk about their ideas, experiences and perspectives.</p>
15:00-15:30	<p>Reviewing the Idea Pool</p> <p>Participants will discuss the idea pool generated in the preceding discussions and vote to prioritise the ideas to be workshopped in the breakout discussions.</p>
15:30-16:00	Break
16:00-16:15	<p>Reviewing the Idea Pool (continued)</p> <p>The results of the vote will be presented and participants will be briefed on the process and themes for the breakout groups.</p>
16:15-17:20	<p>Workshopping Ideas - Breakout group discussions [part 1]</p> <p>Participants will break into small groups to each 'workshop' an idea, model or theme emerging from the discussions.</p> <p>Groups will consider</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The benefits and any aspects that might be problematic; • What would need to change to implement the idea and what the challenges would be; • The key stakeholders that would need to be engaged; • How the idea might practically be piloted and how you might seek to assess its level of success/benefit.
17:20-17:30	Day 1 Wrap Up and Close

Day Two (Wednesday, 20 August 2025)

09:00-09:15	Welcome Plenary: Reflections and Goals for Second Day
09:15-10:15	Workshopping Ideas - Breakout group discussions [part 2] Working Groups continue their discussions and finalise their feedback.
10:15-11:00	Workshop conclusions: plenary discussion Working groups report their key conclusions to plenary, with discussion of the themes emerging
11:00-11:30	Break
11:30-12:30	<p>Plenary Discussion: Moving Forward</p> <p>Moderated discussion to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To what extent are the ideas viable (from a technical, economic and political viewpoint) and which have the potential to be taken forward? • How can we broaden the discussion? Who needs to be involved and what other expertise is required? • What would be the optimal path forward to further develop and pilot these ideas?
12:30-13:00	<p>Closing Discussion: Reflecting and building on the workshop</p> <p>Closing reflections and next steps for reporting, disseminating and promoting further discussion on the meeting outcomes</p>

Appendix B: Workshop Participants

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